

OASEES D.2.2 Decentralized App development for Swarms - Design and specification

Work package	WP2: Requirements and OASEES Architecture
Task	Task 2.2: Decentralized App development for Swarms - Design and specification
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Dissemination level	
Status	Final
Due date	30/06/2024
Document date	28/24/2024
Version number	1.0
 Funded by the European Union	Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Revision and history chart

Version	Date	Main author	Summary of changes
0.1	07/04/2023	Adnan Imeri	Draft table of contents
0.2	08/06/2023	Adnan Imeri	Initial Specification of SC
0.3	30/03/2024	Adnan Imeri/Uwe Roth	Use case responses
0.4	15/04/2024	Adnan Imeri/Uwe Roth	Completing use case specification and smart contract interaction
0.5	15.04.2024	Adnan Imeri/Uwe Roth	Finalizing SC specification
1.0	30.06.2024	Adnan Imeri	Finalization of deliverable

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GLOSSARY OF TERMS

Decentralized Autonomous Organization (DAO) - A DAO is an organization that operates on a blockchain and is governed by smart contracts. It is designed to be autonomous and decentralized, with decision-making processes and operations carried out through consensus mechanisms among its participants.

Decentralized Application (DApp) - A DApp is a type of software that operates on a blockchain in a peer-to-peer manner. Unlike traditional applications that rely on a single central server, the backend of a DApp runs on multiple nodes across the network, enhancing transparency, security, and censorship resistance.

Decentralized Identifier (DID) - A DID is a unique identifier assigned to individuals – or entities – within a decentralized identity system. DIDs enable self-sovereign identity, allowing individuals to control and manage their digital identities across various platforms and services, while maintaining privacy and security.

Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) – DLT is a platform that uses ledgers stored on separate, connected devices in a network to ensure data accuracy and security. Blockchains evolved from distributed ledgers to address growing concerns that too many third parties are involved in too many transactions. DLT is used to securely store data so that it is unaltered, transparent, synchronized, and accurate. This can be extended to counting votes, recording transactions (financial or non-financial) or reporting activity across all users of a single DLT solution.

Ethereum – Ethereum¹ is the community-run technology powering the cryptocurrency ether (ETH) and thousands of decentralized applications. Ethereum is a network made up of many communities and a set of tools which enable people to transact and communicate without being controlled by a central authority. For a user/entity there is no need to hand over all his/its personal details to use it, as the user/entity keeps control of his/its own data and what is being shared. Furthermore, the Ethereum has its own cryptocurrency (known as Ether) which is used to pay for certain activities on the Ethereum network.

Federated (Machine) Learning - FedML² stands for “Fundamental Ecosystem Development/Design for Machine Learning” in a broad scope, and “Federated Machine Learning” in a specific scope. FedML is a unified and scalable distributed computing framework for machine learning anywhere at any scale.

Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) - A digital identity model that emphasizes the individual’s ownership and control over their personal identity information. It allows individuals to create and manage their digital identities independent of any central authority, such as a government, corporation, or social media platform. In SSI, an individual’s identity is represented by a digital credential or set of credentials, which are stored on a secure and decentralized ledger, such as a blockchain. These credentials can contain various pieces of personal information (such as a name, date of birth and address) as well as more sensitive data (like biometric data, health records and financial information). One of the “key” principles of SSI is the concept of “verifiable credentials”, which are cryptographically secured and tamper-proof. This means that the credentials can be easily and securely shared with other parties (such as employers, banks, or online services) without giving them access to the individual’s entire identity information. In summary, self-sovereign identity is a digital identity model that prioritizes individual control and ownership of personal identity information, secured through decentralized and verifiable credentials.

Smart Contract (SC) - A smart contract is a computer code deployed on a blockchain that executes predefined functions and tasks based on specified conditions. It enables automation and trust in transactions, thus eliminating the need for intermediaries and providing transparency and immutability.

Spiking Neural Network (SSN) are artificial neural networks that mimic brain neurons. SNN has been regarded as the third-generation neural network model, closer to the operation mechanism of biological neurons in the brain. SNNs operate using spikes to compute and transmit information which are discrete events that take place at points in time, rather than continuous values. SNNs can significantly improve the energy efficiency of artificial intelligence systems.

Swarm - In the context of OASEES, a swarm refers to a group or network of autonomous agents or devices that collaborate to achieve a common goal. Swarms can exhibit emergent behaviors and self-organize to accomplish complex tasks efficiently and adaptively.

Verifiable Credential (VC) - A verifiable credential is a digital representation of information – or attributes – that can be cryptographically verified. It allows individuals – or entities – to securely “share” selective personal information with trusted verifiers without revealing unnecessary details, thus enhancing privacy and data control.

Zero-knowledge Architecture/Proof - Zero-knowledge architecture/proof is a cryptographic concept that enables the validation of information without revealing the actual data itself. It allows one party (i.e., the “prover”) to prove to another party (i.e., the “verifier”) that certain information – or conditions – are true without disclosing the underlying sensitive data.

Zero-trust Architecture - Zero-trust architecture is an approach to network security that assumes no implicit trust in any user, device, or network component, regardless of its location. It requires continuous authentication and authorization checks for every user and device accessing resources, enhancing security, and reducing the risk of unauthorized access.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

BC - Blockchain

SC – Smart Contract

DAO – Decentralized Autonomous Organization

SSI – Self-Sovereign Identity

VC – Verifiable Credentials

DID – Decentralized Identifiers

ZKP – Zero Knowledge Proofs

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable outlines the high-level requirements for an innovative contract stack for the OASEES. OASEES leverages decentralized infrastructure incorporating swarm intelligence, distributed ledger technology, and blockchain for secure data exchange and collaboration. The resulting OASEES architecture comprises multiple layers, with the Distributed Secure Swarm Layer, in which Decentralized Autonomous Organizations (DAOs) are defined. DAOs combine DApps involving smart contracts to enable trust in swarm environments. The DAO, equipped with Human-in-the-Loop (HITL) mechanisms, facilitates resource management, incentives, and decision-making for swarm collaboration. Users interact with the DAO through digital wallets, token staking, voting on proposals, and receiving rewards.

This deliverable focuses on performing high-level SC specifications. It proposes a design method to enable the extraction of use-case requirements related to smart contract specification. It showcases the interaction of use-case components and potential integration with the overall development framework.

An additional objective of this task will be to define the scientific innovations, contributions, and engineering solutions, including decisions/trade-offs, utilized to realize the OASEES architecture.

INTRODUCTION

This deliverable shows high-level design components that directly contribute to the DApp and SC stack for OASEES' Architecture. Based on the requirements expressed in T2.1, this task aims to perform a high-level design of the components composing the OASEES DApp and SC stack. In the context of D2.1, initial specifications are shown for each use case, including data management (on-chain and off-chain). The aim of D2.2 is to set SC and DApp specifications on a more concrete level, including the SC's detailed specification and their interaction according to use-case requirements.

The efforts in this task will focus on the SC specification and integration with the overall development framework. An additional objective of this task will be to define the scientific innovations, contributions, and engineering solutions, including decisions/trade-offs, utilized to realize the OASEES architecture. This design phase will consider open-source projects and open-source software components available from other projects. This task will also ensure proper communication between all the components by defining interfaces and APIs.

SMART CONTRACTS

The term SC was initially defined by computer scientist Nick Szabo in 1994 as a computerized transaction protocol that executes the terms of a contract.¹ SCs are the fundamental building blocks of Ethereum's application layer.² They are computer programs stored in a blockchain and execute legally binding transactions in accordance with their code. The transaction will be executed automatically, and all participants will have immediate knowledge of the outcome, as there will be no delay or mediator involvement.

SCs represent a significant advancement from transaction-focused blockchains to more interactive technologies. In these systems, the transactions on the blockchain or distributed-ledger technology are dependent upon the terms of the application. According to the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) a SC is a collection of code and data (sometimes referred to as functions and state) that is deployed using cryptographically signed transactions on the blockchain network³. The SC is executed by nodes forming the blockchain network; for the execution to be regarded complete, all nodes must produce identical results. The results of the execution process are recorded on the blockchain. Consensus is used to validate the execution results, which are then recorded on the distributed ledger. SC automation has the potential to accelerate numerous business processes, reduce expenses, and mitigate the risks of fraud and errors.

LEVERAGING OPEN-SOURCE SMART CONTRACTS AS STANDARD TOOLS FOR DEVELOPMENT OF OASEES

OASEES aims to leverage existing open-source solutions that are widely used, adopted, and tested from different application domains to further use and implement OASEES decentralized components. In the Decentralized Autonomous Organization (DAO) and DApp development context, the OASEES' primary reference are SC standards, such as Openzeppelin⁴. However, several adoptions to support the OASEES context are planned for the SC development.

¹ Szabo, N. "Smart Contracts," 1994.

<http://www.fon.hum.uva.nl/rob/Courses/InformationInSpeech/CDROM/Literature/LOTwinterschool2006/szabo.best.vwh.net/smart.contracts.html>

² <https://ethereum.org/en/smart-contracts/#introduction-to-smart-contracts>

³ https://csrc.nist.gov/glossary/term/smart_contract

⁴ <https://www.openzeppelin.com/>

SMART CONTRACT BEST PRACTICES AND SECURITY MEASURES

In this section, we explain the best practices for protecting SC against potential vulnerabilities and attacks. We focus on secure coding practices, access control, data encryption, and input validation.

SC security is not just a task, it's a mission that necessitates thorough design, implementation, testing, monitoring, and analysis. The exposure to vulnerabilities can lead to significant consequences, including financial loss, legal complications, and reputational harm. The diligence in this process is crucial to prevent such risks.

SC are software codes like any other software program. The difference from usual software is how the bugs are fixed. Once an SC has been deployed on the blockchain, it cannot be modified in any way. That is because the blockchain is a distributed ledger; all nodes in the network have a copy of the ledger, and a consensus mechanism guarantees immutability. If an SC were to be modified, it would need to be modified on all network nodes, which is impossible as the consensus maintains the ledger's state and denies unauthorized changes. Consequently, modifications to SCs are only applicable at the moment of deployment.

Several platforms have emerged for developing the SCs, including a standardized approach, security best practices, and many other recommendations. Among them is OpenZeppelin⁵ an open-source platform that provides a wide variety of tools and features that significantly simplify and optimize the process of developing and deploying SCs on the Ethereum blockchain.

RECOMMENDATION TEST VIA TRUFFLE

Truffle⁶ is a programming environment, testing framework, and asset pipeline designed for blockchains utilizing the Ethereum Virtual Machine (EVM) to create and execute SCs on blockchains. It includes tooling to help developers throughout the development cycle, from coding and testing to debugging and deployment. It enables the development of SCs and DApps and allows users to deploy and compile SCs using their preferred RPC client. Support is provided for both network and package management. Truffle is a development environment that utilizes the Ethereum Virtual Machine. Consequently, it is possible to do testing and development quickly. Developers can utilize the SC by uploading the Solidity code, which is compiled by Truffle, to the Ethereum network. To incorporate changes made to SCs on a local blockchain environment such as Ganache or other test networks, it is necessary to do a new compilation and deployment. Redeploying an SC involves replacing the existing code of the network's SC with a completely new contract.

The Truffle Suite's three distinct components, Truffle, Ganache and Drizzle provide a robust ecosystem that is highly favored by numerous DApp developers. Ganache is utilized throughout the development cycle, allowing users to create, distribute, and test DApps in a secure and consistent framework. Ganache provides a range of useful features, including the creation of new accounts, the ability to send transactions and the capability to debug SCs. By effectively identifying and fixing errors in their SC code, developers can use Ganache as a debugging tool to accelerate the development process. Drizzle is a collection of front-end libraries with the aim of simplifying and increasing the predictability of connecting the DApp's front-end to the Ethereum network.

MetaMask is a software cryptocurrency wallet that enables users to interact with the Ethereum blockchain network through a browser extension or mobile app. MetaMask functions as a bridge for web applications to communicate with the Ethereum network, allowing users to stay anonymous because it does not require personal information to create an account. One of MetaMask's main advantages is that it provides access to decentralized applications in the browser without running a full Ethereum node. MetaMask supports most blockchains, NFTs, and all ERC-20

⁵ <https://www.openzeppelin.com/>

⁶ <https://trufflesuite.com/docs/truffle/>

tokens. It allows users to store and manage Ethereum and ERC-20 tokens securely, send and receive tokens easily, access and manage Ethereum SCs, and provide secure access to the Ethereum blockchain⁷.

DEEP-LEARNING BASED SMART-CONTRACT VULNERABILITY DETECTION

As mentioned above, the security of SCs is a matter of utter importance. We are developing deep-learning techniques for adaptable vulnerability detection in the SCs that will be implemented within the OASEES framework. Recognizing the critical need for robust vulnerability-detection mechanisms, recent research has leveraged advanced deep-learning (DL) techniques to achieve this goal.

Traditional automated vulnerability-detection tools, such as Oyente⁸, Mythril⁹, Slither¹⁰, and SmartCheck (Tikhomirov, 2018), predominantly rely on static analysis and symbolic execution techniques to identify potential vulnerabilities in SCs. Static analysis involves scrutinizing the source code without executing it, aiming to uncover vulnerabilities by identifying patterns and known risky constructs. Symbolic analysis, on the other hand, employs symbolic execution to explore all possible paths of a program, symbolically executing code with symbolic inputs to detect vulnerabilities. While these tools have proven valuable in many cases, they come with inherent limitations. Static analysis tools often result in false positives and false negatives because of their high reliance on predefined rules and lack of semantic analysis capabilities. Symbolic execution, while powerful, can be computationally expensive and may not scale well with the complexity of large SCs.

In contrast, a deep learning-based approach offers a paradigm shift by leveraging neural networks to automatically learn patterns and features indicative of vulnerabilities from vast amounts of training data. Deep learning models, such as recurrent neural networks (RNNs) or long short-term memory networks (LSTMs), excel in capturing intricate relationships within data and can adapt to the evolving nature of SC vulnerabilities. By learning from the inherent complexity and variability of SC behaviors, deep learning models can provide a more nuanced and accurate assessment, potentially reducing false positives and improving overall detection efficacy. The adaptability and continuous-learning capabilities of deep learning make it an attractive choice for enhancing the efficiency and effectiveness of vulnerability detection in the context of DAOs and SC security.

Gao et al. introduced an automated method for analyzing Solidity SCs through structural code embedding. Their approach leverages word embeddings and vector-space comparison to parse smart-contract code into word streams that include code structural information. By converting code elements into numerical vectors, this method aims to encapsulate the syntax and semantics of the code, facilitating the identification of potential issues by comparing similarities among these vectors and known bugs. In another innovative approach, Zhang et al. proposed a method that combines information graph techniques with ensemble learning for smart-contract vulnerability detection. They also developed the Serial-Parallel Convolutional Bidirectional Gated Recurrent Network Model incorporating Ensemble Classifiers (SPCBIG-EC), specifically targeting enhanced detection capabilities in IoT devices.

Furthermore, the use of pre-trained models and novel feature-extraction techniques has been explored for enhancing the detection capabilities. For instance, Zhang et al. utilized pre-trained BERT models and opcode-based co-occurrence matrices to extract explicit and implicit features of SCs, showcasing the potential of leveraging pre-existing language models and unique characteristics of smart-contract code for vulnerability detection. Liao et al. adopted a different approach by using N-gram language modeling and term frequency-inverse document frequency (tf-idf) feature vectors to represent smart-contract source code. This method facilitated the training of traditional machine-learning models to identify 13 types of vulnerabilities, employing a gray-box fuzz testing mechanism for real-time transaction validation, indicating the effectiveness of combining statistical language models with machine

⁷ <https://wallets.com/metamask-review/#review>

⁸ <https://github.com/enzymefinance/oyente>

⁹ <https://github.com/Consensys/mythril>

¹⁰ <https://github.com/crytic/slither>

learning for vulnerability detection. Lastly, Huang et al. introduced a novel model using convolutional neural networks (CNN) to detect vulnerabilities in SCs. This approach transforms the binary representation of vulnerable code into RGB images, which are then processed through CNN. This innovative method highlights the versatility of machine learning approaches in detecting vulnerabilities by adapting techniques from the field of image processing.

Building upon the current landscape of research, the OASEES project aims to contribute to the field of SC vulnerability detection through the development of a Multimodal Smart-Contract Vulnerability-Detection Deep-Learning model. These modalities include textual information, such as Solidity source code, and visual information, represented by Solidity bytecode translated into RGB images. By employing a dual-modality framework, our goal is to leverage the complementary strengths of both textual code analysis and image-based representations of SCs. This strategy underscores our objective to achieve a more comprehensive analysis by capturing the intricate details present in the code's syntax and semantics, as well as the structural patterns that can be represented visually. The integration of text and image modalities in our model is based on the premise that the combination of these data types can uncover vulnerabilities with greater accuracy and depth than single-modality approaches. Through this bimodal methodology, the OASEES project aims to contribute to the field by enhancing the precision of vulnerability detection and addressing the complexities inherent in smart-contract security. Our initiative seeks to explore the synergistic potential of text and image data in uncovering nuanced vulnerabilities, reflecting a commitment to advancing the capabilities of deep learning in ensuring the integrity of SCs.

DECENTRALIZED APPLICATION (DAPP) FOR THE OASEES CONTEXT

The definition of the DApp and its characteristics are presented in D.2.1, section “Definition of decentralized application and its architecture”.

In the context of specifying the DApp for the use case, we perform SC specification with the aim of serving as an expression of operation within the use case, which the DApp will exploit.

DAO GOVERNANCE IN THE CONTEXT OF OASEES

The general characteristics of the DAO Governance in the context of the OASEES are presented in D2.1.

In the context of D2.2, we present an advanced specification of a DAO proposal that needs to be governed by general DAO governance and management. The general DAO governance has the necessary operational mechanism to support any DAO-decision process via proposals.

OASEES: SMART CONTRAT SPECIFICATION BASED ON GIVEN REQUIREMENTS FROM USE CASE

This section highlights the specification of the SC for the OASEES use case requirements. It is composed of 6 subsections representing OASEES use cases.

METHODOLOGY FOR DESIGNING AND SPECIFICATION OF THE OASEES SMART CONTRACT STACK

Notably, in software engineering, including SC engineering, the specification determines what the SC will do and what requirements it needs to fulfill.

This section outlines a thorough methodology to explore, analyze, and extract functional requirements for the OASEES DApp and SC stack. This methodology is designed to achieve a high-level design and specification of the

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DApp and SC stack. The deterministic nature of DApps, where specific outputs are generated for given inputs, is a key element of this methodology. The SC stack design and specification for OASEES aims to clarify terms, conditions, and actions to be executed within the SC (DApp). We also aim to clarify the actors, preconditions, and postconditions for executing specific SC functions, evidencing triggers, and expected outcomes for the SC executions. This methodology is structured in four main steps, as follows:

S1: Reading Initial Requirements Book¹¹

As an entry point for the OASEES SC design and specification, we consider requirements expressed from the use-case definitions (D2.1), mainly the use-case requirements, expressed as functional requirements.

S2: Extending Requirements Book

This step enables highlighting specific requirements from the use-case perspective to be extended to allow detailed functionality.

S3: Feasibility study for expression of the requirements of use case into SC

As the use case requirements are expressed as preconditional forms, we initially perform a feasibility study to convert them into functional requirements. Therefore, in this step, we aim to extract functional requirements related to DAO and SC (DApp).

By conducting the feasibility study, we are able to clearly define the purpose and objectives of the SC. This includes identifying the problems to be solved, the actions to be performed, and the expected outcomes.

S4: Exclusion (overlapping)

The predefined specification that are already defined, such as unique identification of actors and devices in the OASEES framework, to avoid redundancy.

S5: Expression of Requirements (Formal Modelling of the SC)

- Sequential Diagram
 - SC-functions specification
 - Confirmation by UC owner
- As a design practice, we aim to keep the SC logic as simple as possible by breaking down the SC specification into modular pieces. Thus, we avoid complex functions of the SC while avoiding bugs and vulnerabilities.

S6: Interaction schemas of involved parties on DApp

This step helps specify the SC's interaction schema with involved parties, including external parties. Indeed, this involves designing an API or UI specific to how the interaction (executing/invoking SC function or access to SC data) with SC occurs.

¹¹ We refer to the requirements book, which is the initial description of the use case characteristics performed by use case owners.

SMART CONTRACT SPECIFICATION FOR COMPOSING THE OASEES DAPP AND SMART CONTRACT STACK

This section shows the SC specification based on the extracted requirements and data management from the use-case perspective. Initially, we show an extended use-case diagram and perform formal specifications based on the sequential diagram for each use case. The main intention of this deliverable is to specify DAO and DApp for each use case for the OASEES.

UC1: SMART EDGE-CONNECTED NODE FOR THE ANALYSIS OF VOICE, ARTICULATION AND FLUENCY DISORDER IN PARKINSON'S DISEASE

The usability of the DAO in the context of UC1 fosters a collaborative environment, where all stakeholders are included and contribute to the decision-making process. This significantly enhances the collaboration of the parties involved and proposes impactful changes for patients. As DAO participants, we have a set of professional therapists who are part of such a collaboration. The value of DAO as a collaboration and decision-making tool is evident when applying a specific "therapy" to a patient. Based on the patient's "behavior", i.e., level of illness (Parkinson's level could be determined with some range) and scores for that level of illness, professionals (therapists) could vote on which therapy (named and added by Human in the Loop (HITL)) they agree to apply to the patient (to maintain a low level of Parkinson in a patient). HITL can play a significant role by initiating such voting. HITL can be a medical institution, professional organization, speech therapist, or any other role granted by a specific authority.

Therefore, the composition of the UC1 is done by the following identified phases:

Phase 1 (data collection): In phase 1, data is collected to train the AI algorithms. Audio files are created for each word or sentence the patient speaks and annotated by at least 2 (up to 4) speech therapists. The annotation gives scores that must be met by the AI algorithm once deployed. Voting is carried out in the DAO by the speech therapists to accept or reject the recorded data (and annotation) for training. Each exercise will have various levels of complexity (syllables, simple words, complex words, sentences, etc.). The patient, as well as the speech therapist, have IDs. Each session (exercise) gets a unique identification number. Audio files and annotations must be shared between the stakeholders (sharing between speech therapists).

Phase 2 (deployment phase): In the deployment phase, there will be the onboarding process of the devices, patients, speech therapists, and potentially system providers. Each of these stakeholders has a specific ID. The trained model is uploaded via the DAO on the device. After set-up, the patient does exercises (at home), and the results in the form of scores (calculated by the algorithm) are uploaded to the DAO. The speech therapists can access this data (ideally graphically enhanced by an external graphical interface) and make decisions in the form of votes on how to adapt the exercises to be done by the patient. An SC need to be established between the patient and the speech therapist, as well as between the patient or the speech therapist and a third-party hardware or software provider.

Phase 3 (federated learning):

Phase 3 aims to be developed progressively based on results discovered from previous phases. However, we propose some foundation related to the involved actors in this phase, as follows:

- Speech Therapist or HITL (Unique ID)
- Patient (Unique ID)
- Edge Device (Unique ID)
- Developer (Scientist) Phase (3)

Use Case Diagram for UC1

Figure 1 shows the use-case diagram extracted from the initial specification of UC1 (D2.1). It represents the main components and their interaction.

Figure 1: The use-case diagram for UC1.

In the section below, we express UC1 component interactions. These interactions are further exploited in the SC definition.

SC STACK: UC1 COMPONENT INTERACTION FOR SMART CONTRACT AND DAPP SPECIFICATION

Initially, we extract DAO-based activities that should be used to manage swarm intelligence. We express the aim and operational activities of the DAO.

- UC1: DAO activities for swarm intelligence.** The set of activities expressed via DAO via proposals and the invocation of the DApp.
 - o proposal: share scores from the exercise
 - o proposal: adapt next exercise based on result received
 - o proposal: register new edge devices (onboarding should be carried out by relevant entity)
 - o proposal: remove existing edge devices
 - o proposal: registration of practitioners (speech therapist)
 - o proposal: update of diagnostic algorithm when a newly trained version is available
 - o smart contract: monitor device activities
 - o smart contract: grant access to data for practitioners
 - o smart contract: incentive model proposals for activity members
 - treasury smart contract
 - o smart contract: grant access to data for specific DApp (HITL)

2. Interaction of the whole smart contract stack and other components.

The diagram presented in Figure 2 shows the components used and the formal specifications of the interaction of

components to fulfill requirements expressed in D2.1 regarding UC1. Such specification aims to express functional specifications for the OASEES DAO and DApp (i.e., SC Stack) related to UC1. In the following, we express each component, their characteristics, and interactions between such components.

Session:

Each evaluation session shall take unique identification. This is initiated and finalized by activities “initiate session” via interaction with smart contract.

Patients:

- Patient identification (based on the OASEES Identity Layer)
 - Initially, the patient requests authentication via SSI-based wallet (Web3 Wallet).
 - Patient credentials are stored on the Patient Wallet.
- Patients can “rent” or “use” specific device from third parties, via “request device” which can be used to monitor level of disease. In such case, the patient can initiate payment via “initiate payment” towards third-party service (device) provider.
- Patients can plug in edge devices and perform speech monitoring. These edge devices have the capacity to perform monitoring, send information (store in IPFS for further analysis) and notify speech therapist for the score calculated (based on their algorithm). This activity is performed based on “self-made exercise”, followed a DAO “proposal: automatic score upload” initiate device. For further analysis specific sets of data are stored in Private IPFS by using “store information”. Further, for traceability and data immutability, hashing of data is stored in blockchain via “store hashes to bc device reg”, which is further published on DAO as data reference via “publish hash: data reference”.

Speech Therapist/Practitioner

- Speech Therapists should be identified to access OASEES framework (based on the OASEES Identity Layer). For each speech therapist an onboarding process should be completed “onboarding speech therapist”.
 - Authentication:
 - A speech therapist can be authenticated as HITL for the DAO voting.
 - General speech therapist who performs some tests.
 - As data collector (performing tests with patients).
 - Activities:
 - Initiate DAO proposals for: device onboarding/removal, study (test) to be used by speech therapists, upload and update study scores.
 - Initiate tests (study) with patients, which is done by accessing specific data and performing data annotation via “annotate data”.
 - Generate and publish scores of the test (study) which is done via “publish scores”.
 - Update scores for new study.
 - Votes for score/study to be used next.
- The speech therapist is required to follow automatic activities performed by specific edge device and decide on publishing exercise that need to be applied in future cases. These activities are performed by “proposal: adept new exercise”, where other speech therapists can decide by voting on this proposal i.e., “DAO: voting members”.
- Payments. Therapists shall require payment for the time spent on the analysis of the tests (voice). This activity is pre-determined based on hourly rates (or based on HITL/organization) and payment is initiated via “request payment”. Any speech therapist involved in such a process can ask for payment. These requests are placed as DAO “proposal: therapist payment” and with the voting process, mainly HITL, the payment is executed. In such cases HITL plays a major role in payment processing.

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- A speech therapist can propose new edge devices to be included in the study. This process is covered by DAO “proposal: new device”. DAO members, i.e., speech therapists vote on accepting or denying tests via this device.

Edge Device:

- Device authentication (DID Method) (based on the OASEES Identity Layer)
- A process of onboarding process via the “onboarding device” for each device should be completed in all cases:
 - Speech Therapist deployed devices.
 - Rented devices from third party.
 - Generate voice data and store them into private IPFS/Database
 - **ORACLE:**
 - Access device to IPFS for voice data storage
 - Device to DAO for score publication
- Phase 3: Uploading specific algorithms to the device.

Once newly trained algorithms are available, a vote is performed before updating is allowed on the swarm devices.

IPFS/Database

- Used to store data generated from tests.

User/Developer (Phase 3): This part presents a business logic that potential users might be interested in working with such data.

Any verified profile who works with ML/AI libraries to improve the model for Parkinson's disease:

- Request access to data via “request data access” which is granted (or deny) by HITL (grant/deny access)
- The profile potentially might come with new scores “proposal: new scores” which can be evaluated by DAO members and HITL. Based on voting and decision-making by HITL the developer will be notified for the “proposal: final results”.
- If the scores are accepted, then the developer is allowed to “publish/share referential model”
- The HITL and DAO members can proceed with payment for this model via “payment processed for dev”.

Figure 2: Expression of SC stack interaction and other components for UC1.

C2: EVS FLEET COORDINATED RECHARGING TO SUPPORT OPTIMAL OPERATION OF ELECTRICITY

UC2 proposes a swarm intelligence-based solution supported by DAO to manage energy consumption and optimize the energy grid. Figure 3 shows the use case diagram extracted from the initial specification of UC2 (D2.1).

The use case describes an electricity-grid scenario. On the one hand, renewable energy-based photovoltaic plants are added to the grid, producing energy beyond needs. In contrast, on the other hand, to reduce potential grid tensions, a massive demand for electric vehicles to consume energy during vehicle charging is encouraged. That creates some demands for additional optimization to bring the provisioning and consumption of energy into balance, and certainly the need to minimize energy grid tensions. In case too much energy is produced by the photovoltaic plants, electric vehicles should be used to consume that additional energy by charging their battery. Suppose such an event is forecast and intervention is required. In that case, the energy grid creates an energy-flexibility request—potentially, different e-mobility service providers answer that request with a price offer. In the case of energy-flexibility trading, the marketplace selects the best offer with the lowest price, which results in minor costs. The electric-vehicle providers (stations) and owners are then informed about the specific charging schedule. In the scenario, several actors are relevant:

- **DSO** - Distributed System Operator / Electricity Network Operator - Manages the energy grid
- **eMSP** - e-Mobility Service Provider - Manages the business side of the changing network with its charging stations for electric vehicles (customers and monetizing EV charging)
- **CPO** - Charging Point Operator - Builds, manages and maintains the charging network with the charging stations
- Electric Vehicle owner / fleet operator - Owner of electric vehicles

Additionally, there are some known involved systems:

- **EV** - Electric Vehicles
- **CS** - Charging Stations
- **Smart Meter**. The charging stations' smart meters allow real-time readings of their energy consumption data. Their data verifies energy-flexibility provision; based on that data, a smart contract will be closed, and transactions will be performed. The energy grid's smart meter data and EV data are used to verify the energy-flexibility needs (DSO side) and the energy-flexibility potential provision (eMSP side).

It is foreseen to setup several new platforms, systems, and components:

- **EMP** - Electronic Mobility Platform, managed by the eMSP. Hosts charging stations. Hosts electric vehicles. Shows real-time and historical data of IoT devices.
- **DSO Platform** - for managing DSO activities.
- **P2P** - Marketplace - P2P energy flexibility trading. It hosts multiple eMSPs.
- **DLT with DAO** Distributed Autonomous Organization
- **DApp** - Decentralized Application
- **Forecasting Systems** - estimating energy production and energy consumption / needs
- **Dashboards** at DSO platform and electric-mobility platform - Provide access to the P2P Marketplace. Show real-time payment data. Manage access control.

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Figure 3: The use-case diagram for UC2.

SC STACK: UC2 COMPONENT INTERACTION FOR SMART CONTRACT AND DAPP SPECIFICATION

In depth DAO enables collective collaboration towards a common objective. In the case of UC2, one of the main objectives is to enable an extensive collaboration between DSO, CPO, EV operators and drivers to enable optimal energy consumption.

1. UC2: DAO Activities/Proposals for swarm intelligence. The set of activities expressed via DAO via proposals and the invocation of the DApp:

- proposal: prices proposed by DSO
- proposal: register new edge devices (onboarding should be carried out by relevant entity)
- proposal: remove existing edge devices
- proposal: incentive model proposals for activity members (calling another SC)
 - treasury smart contract
- proposal: remove and add any organization!
- proposal: choose the selling price of each CPO
 - Specify payment time (if needed)
 - Specify condition for payment!
- proposal: choose the lower selling price
- smart contract / proposal: data-sharing rules (update, add, remove)
- smart contract / proposal: access control and management (drives, other involved). To indicate which data can be accessed by different actors.

2. Interaction of the whole smart contract stack and other components.

Figure 4 presents the interaction schema for the SC activities, DAO and other involved components.

Identification:

The process starts by identifying involved parties, particularly DSO, CPO eMSP, CP, and users of such platforms. The OASEES Identity Layer (DID Method) performs the identification process.

Edge Device:

- Smart Meter device shall be identified (DID Method).
- Smart Meter “read data” from CS.
 - **ORACLE**: access data to third party service and transfer it to blockchain.
- CS “provide data” for Smart Meter and for CPO.
 - Data are stored in IPFS “data storage”.

Interaction/data sharing:

- eMSP “inform DSO” for any business activities changing in the network.
- The DSO shall “request data/provide data” to CPO and data are stored in IPFS via the “provide data, charging scheduling”. These data shall be used for other business logic.
- The EV will provide data via “provide data” to the IPFS which are further accessed for business process.
- DApp/Smart Contract can access data in IPFS and store hash of such data to blockchain via “store hashing: smart meter, EV Data, CS”.
- EV driver can receive information for charging options, i.e., “inform drivers for new schedules”.
- DSO can access data at any time via “request data for charging station”.
- Then from IPFS perspective, API or ORACLE will be called to store data via the “notification for provided data”.
- DSO shall forecast data into DAO via “forecast energy related data”, these data shall be accessed from DApp via “forecast electricity production/consumption data”
- DSO can propose new prices for eMSP via “trigger proposal for price offering” and involved parties are notified e.g., eMSP “inform EMP”.
- Further notification is distributed “notify for price offering” for the new review.
- DAO members can vote for the proposal “inf. for price accept/reject”.
- DAO proposals are indicated, and the general voting/notification process is applied.
- Micropayment execution. This process is performed via “execute micro payment”. The micro payment can be initiated by a specific actor e.g., DSO.

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Figure 4: Expression of SC stack interaction and other components for UC2

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From the DApp perspective, this use case presents a unique opportunity for multi-communication within CPO, fostering energy consumption and optimization. In a collaborative effort with UC2 owners, we propose a DApp that holds the potential to significantly enhance UC2 operations.

From the DApp perspective, we propose the incorporation of the charging station and drivers by allowing them to share their availabilities to charge their cars in specific charging stations. That would be performed via a proposal (initially by checking if the precondition is fulfilled, e.g., availability at the charging station at that time, capacity of the charging station, etc.), which is sent to DAO (voted by members and HITL). Once the proposal is approved, EV drivers can charge EVs in the proposed time intervals. The charging station receive some incentives in selling the whole electricity. The DApp (relying on SC) performs matchmaking (a combination of off-chain and on-chain) and notifies the EV drivers. This aims to include EV drivers in swarm intelligence. It shall also be used to change and monitor energy prices. Specific functions shall be used for data logging from user (stakeholders) interactions.

UC3: DRONE SWARM OVER 5G FOR HIGH MAST INSPECTION

The use case describes the inspection of a high mast via a swarm of drones. It leverages the security and reliability of blockchain technology to enhance data transparency and sharing, particularly in the context of drone inspection of the mast. This enables all stakeholders to access and rely on optimized data (routing) for mast inspection. The high-level interaction of the involved concepts for this use case is illustrated in Figure 5, where multiple entities collaborate to facilitate high mast inspection.

In the scenario, several actors are relevant:

- **UAV Controller / Drone Operator / Pilot.**
Provides the coordination of the Drone Swarm.
It also provides the flight plan to be executed, either based on Quantum Processing Unit (QPU) optimization, or DAO governance.
Acts as the Human-in-the-loop (HITL) actor in the DAO, which may enforce certain actions in the DAO operation, e.g., Emergency Landing.
The Jupyter Notebook Software-Development Kit (SDK) in the portal triggers the QPU and executes Qrisp-related functions. Once an experiment is executed, the SDK sends the optimized route to the controller.
- **UAV Service Supplier.** DAO infrastructure provider, supplying the drone-swarm devices. Will publish and support the onboarding process of the Drone Swarm to the DAO.
- **Tower company.**
- **Third-Party Authorization Entity.**

Additionally, there are some known systems:

- **Drone / Drone Swarm.**
Proposal for path recalculation, triggered by the SNN object detection.
QPU provides the optimized route that would be enforced in the DAO swarm.
Logical voting on proposal.
- **Agent.** Part of the drone
 - Agent (identity). Verifies itself after boot with the local trust issuer / local SSI service.
The successful operation of this will result in the assignment/issuance of the wallet ID for this drone. The **wallet ID** will be generated from the locally deployed DLT and will also be mapped/assigned as a member of the relevant DAO.
 - Agent (energy consumption). Provides real-time energy consumption to the DAO.
 - Agent (voting) to perform different interactions with the DAO.
- **SNN (Spiking Neural Network)**
 - Edge Accelerator, located in the drone.
 - Energy efficient object and pattern detection.
 - Detect an object and, based on that, to re-organize the flight to better inspect such an object.
- **QPU Quantum Processing Unit**
 - Edge Accelerator.
 - Cloud-centralized function on the cloud part of OASEES.
 - Solves travelling salesman problem.
 - Has two options for optimization: Route or job schedule.
 - Given the step where the drones have been onboarded in the DAO (i.e., the infrastructure has been defined), the programmer can have access through the SDK, load up an indicative coordinate graph and feed it to Qrisp (QPU).
 - The optimized output is then fed to the flight manager to perform the optimized route.
- **UAS Unmanned Aerial System.** Acts as the middleware to load onto the drone swarm the flight plan to follow. It will support two modes of operation and decision making:
 - Coordinate the drone swarm to follow the optimized route plan, calculated by the QPU.

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- Re-calculate and update the flight plan to the new one, based on a proposal submitted by one of the drone members of the DAO, if it gets passed and executed.
- **SSI Service.** Local SSI service and trust issuer.

It is foreseen to setup several new platforms, systems, and components:

- **DLT/DAO**

Issue tokens that will provide governance utility to the drones so they can propose and vote.

The operator, with a larger number of tokens, plays a pivotal role in our governance system. Their tokens are instrumental in enforcing decisions.

In the case of object detection, drones will vote based on their battery life whether they can make the trip to the destination. Alternatively, they can abstain from the vote to potentially be omitted from the flight plan.

The DAO can propose an optimal route derived from QPU.

- **OASEES stack**

Each pilot infrastructure deploys the OASEES stack. For now, some cloud functions will be hosted in NCSR.D.

Currently provides a backend DAO function and the agent for the devices.

The agent will run on each drone, and the device will be onboarded in the DAO. Therefore, the DAO will operate as an infrastructure manager as a first basis.

- **Monitoring Backend**

A telegraph-based monitoring agent. It will not make any decisions, but based on the data stored, the DAO will be able to create proposals.

Incorporate the proposed monitoring (Telegraf from TEC), pull data (DAO) and make decisions.

No decisions will be made by the monitoring backend.

Located in the cloud and it collects data from the agents.

Figure 5: The use-case diagram for UC3.

SC STACK: UC3 COMPONENT INTERACTION FOR SMART CONTRACT AND DAPP SPECIFICATION

1. **UC3: DAO activities/proposals for swarm intelligence for UC3.** The set of activities expressed via DAO via proposals and the invocation of the DApp.

- proposal: register new drone (onboarding should be carried out by relevant entity)
 - allocate X^{12} quantity of tokens
- proposal: remove existing drone
 - drain X quantity of tokens
- proposal: loading new routes to drone
- proposal: incentive model proposals for activity members (calling another SC)
 - treasury smart contract
- smart contract: grant access to data for specific DApp (HITL)
- smart contract: monitor drone activity

2. **Interaction of the whole smart contract stack and other components.**

Figure 6 expresses some of the main interactions in a sequential diagram.

Drone Operator (HITL):

- Operate drone and “request new routing data”.
- Register any drone as DAO member “register drone as members of DAO”
- Request new drone routing “request new routing data”
- Engage routing algorithm via “load initial routing data”
- Manage technological component e.g., Databases/IPFS

Optimization ALG

- Presents initial routing algorithm
- Presents optimized routing algorithm via “provide data optimization alg.”

DApp/Smart Contract

- Initiate inspection
- Request data access

¹² The exact number of tokens is determined once the DAO governances is determined.

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Figure 6: Expression of SC stack interaction and other components for UC3.

UC4: STRUCTURAL-SAFETY ASSESSMENT FOR BUILDINGS

Sensor data of structural conditions of buildings and infrastructure are evaluated by a specialized decision-support system (DSS) called Night Watch (NW) during and after earthquake events¹³. Such data must be verified, filtered, corrected, and interpreted before the system makes conclusions.

During an earthquake event, the amount of data produced leads to a delay of arrival in the DSS and a delay in conclusions that can be drawn. Furthermore, the trigger (the decision whether an earthquake happened or not) must be given quickly when the data is collected. This operation is much more reliable and quicker if performed at the edge.

The goal is to move logic to the edge devices and embed the NW-DSS at the edge.

In case the NW-DSS identifies an earthquake via the NW Prelim module or has been informed about it by the earthquake agency (see Appendix 1 for the detailed explanation of the triggering logic), the NW-DSS triggers the DAO of a blockchain/DLT to start a reporting process, which puts the edge devices into swarm mode. The edge devices then upload sensor data to the IPFS, keeping only their hash values in the DAO as evidence. The edge devices perform filtering and signal-processing actions on the data and cross-correlate the data to ensure reliability, consistency, and accuracy. Processed data, as well as collected features, are uploaded to the DAO. The DAO takes the data to initiate a decision process that results in a report and advice for actions that a Human in the Loop (HITL) must evaluate. The evaluation result (e.g., classification as an aftershock or new earthquake) is communicated to the DAO. It might impact the further analysis of the newly arriving data or stop the swarm mode.

In the context of UC4, the usability of DAO aims to enable decision-making efficiency. DAO helps to reduce latency compared to centralized systems. The algorithmic implementation and improved data access aim to improve decision making at the first stage in case of an event. Further, it enhances the performance of notification aspects in an earthquake event, giving emergency teams necessary information for a potential emergency intervention.

The added value in the OASEES context of the implementation of UC4 aims to significantly improve communication with clients (critical type of clients, especially, such as Izmir Airport, Avrasya Tunnel, etc., and their management as well as search-and-rescue teams), which in another case might not have the specific earthquake-related information in case of a significant event. In normal circumstances, these clients shall only receive this information from government agencies after longer periods of time, within the critical post-disaster minutes and even hours. UC4 aims to provide such information for its clients in almost real time¹⁴ in case of an event. Contrary to that, the main added values in UC4 are “reliability” and “speed” in delivering critical information to the client in the first minute(s) after a serious earthquake. This can play a life-saving role and protect property and assets better than the centralized system we have at the moment.

In the scenario, several actors are relevant:

- **Customer** - Hosts multiple sensors.
- **HITL** - Human in the Loop. Decision maker. Takes decisions based on decision support.

Additionally, there are some known systems:

- **Smart Edge Device / Accelerator** - Runs Decentralized Application DApp.
- **Federated learning** for information collection/features (pre-treated) and sharing it with other Smart Edge Devices. Identified via a DID.

¹³ Note: In the context of UC4m an earthquake is called an “event”.

¹⁴ The concept of the real time for the case of an event is defined based on specific conditions of information retrieval.

- **Intra-Structure Sensor** allows internal scanning of objects

It is foreseen to setup several new platforms, systems and components:

- **NW - Night Watch** - Monitors structures before, during and after an event.
The NightWatch will be placed on each sensor or a few clusters of sensors (depending on how close the sensors are placed to each other, on cabling, etc.).
- **DSS – Decision-Support System**. Verifies, filters, corrects, and interprets raw sensor data.
- **OASEES Supported Architecture** with DAO governance and process optimization.
- **Dashboard** - controls all the NightWatch clients
Controls the NightWatch clones running at each location (i.e., for regularly collecting failure reports, checking if all sensors are functioning, etc.).
Collect the individual models from each NightWatch to update a global model.
Collect data from various sensors to manually train a model.

Important data structures and their transformation:

- **Raw Sensor Data:** Collected by the Sensors.
- **Clean Sensor Data (pre-treated data).** Verified, filtered, and corrected raw data by the Night Watch System, stored in the database of the smart-edge device.
- **Processed Data.** Interpreted version of the clean data created by the Night Watch System, stored in the IPFS.
- **Event Data Hashes.** Summary/array of processed data created by the Night Watch System, stored in the blockchain.

Figure 7 presents the detailed use-case diagram related to UC4. This diagram shows the involvement of components and the interaction between them, as well as data-sharing context.

Figure 7: The use-case diagram for UC4.

SC STACK: UC4 COMPONENT INTERACTION FOR SMART CONTRACT AND DAPP SPECIFICATION

From the expression of the use case above, we extract the interaction schema as shown in Figure 8. Initially we show DAO, DApp and other component interactions.

1. **UC4: DAO activities/proposals for swarm intelligence for UC4.** The set of activities expressed via DAO via proposals and the invocation of the DApp.
 - HITL proposal: algorithm for safety/decision measurement. This proposal aims to load or trace a specific algorithm.
 - HITL proposal: register changes on NW algorithm. Once the initial algorithm has been specified, any improvement needs to be verified by DAO members or HITL and all changes evidenced shall be traced.
 - HITL proposal: remove/register new swarm edge devices (onboarding should be carried out by relevant entity).
 - DApp/smart contract proposal: “request data access”.
 - DApp/smart contract proposal: enable DApp activities such as reporting, triggering data based on specific events. Once a proposal is accepted then DAO monitors all transactions to ensure transparency over any process.
 - DApp/smart contract proposal: communicate with swarm edge device engaging specific activity from DApp.

2. **Interaction of the whole smart contract stack and other components.**

Figure 8 shows interactions between components involved in UC4. These interactions reflect activities related to data sharing based on several events happening related to UC4 description.

Smart Edge Device

- Smart Edge Device is authenticated via DID Method and associated with DAO as trusted device.
- Smart Edge Device authenticates other sensors via “authenticate and authorize sensors”.
- Smart Edge Devices sends data into IPFS via “store data received from sensors” and hash of data into blockchain (DAO) via “update storage buffer”.
- Smart Edge Devices sense data from deployed sensor “event/data from sensor” and trigger a report “trigger report” towards DAO.
- Based on DAO report, edge devices shall be able to notify specific teams (part of DAO) via the “notify teams/specific action”.
-

HITL - Human in the Loop

- Propose new decision based on proposed actions from Smart Edge Devices “check actions”
- Changing NW configuration via “changing NW config/alg”. This is done via DAO proposal where a new algorithm is proposed for event monitoring.
- HITL can play the role of External Agency.

External Agencies

- These agencies enable quick reaction in case of an event. They use DApp “access DApp/SC”. They can store data via “store data: rescue teams info., structural assessment”. These data are crucial in case of an event.

DApp/Smart Contract

- Enables external agencies (users) specific activities to adapt via “engaging specific activity”.

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- Enables to propose any “propose activity” related to events via DAO
- DApp might request data access via “request data access” which can be granted by DAO via “data/activity-granted/denied”
- DApp/smart contract shall generate specific report based on specific event from “Smart Edge Device” via “trigger report”. Parameters of invoking a specific smart contract can be discovered based on specific events.

Figure 8: Expression of SC stack interaction and other components for UC4.

UC5: ROBOTIC-SWARM POWERED FACTORY FOR I4.0

The use case covers the automated manufacturing process for semi-finished wood as part of furniture production and its processing until assembly. Figure 9 shows the use-case diagram for UC5. It presents different components involved in this use case.

The DAO helps with automatic parameter adaptation by using the decentralized capabilities of DAO for collection sets or parameters from different devices and automatically adjusting them to specific algorithms within the OASEES stack. Further, the gathered parameters (data) enable the “formulization” of the DAO proposal, which can be reviewed by the operator (HITL), and decisions are taken based on them. Another aspect is the “collaborative” cooperation of devices via DAO instructions. Once the HITL has proposed an update on the instruction, these are distributed in linked devices without any need to separately give/adapt instructions to the devices (autonomous mobile robots (AMRs)). Indeed, this adaptation is performed with the help of the OASEES orchestrator. Also, from the security and safety viewpoint, having a set of devices authenticated (identified), we certify that only specific (identified) devices receive updated instructions at all certain levels of safety with respect to avoiding misbehavior.

Figure 9: The use-case diagram for UC5.

In the scenario, the following actors are relevant:

- **Operator** - Human in the Loop (HITL). Defines requirements and instructions. Approves or rejects proposals. Accesses real-time data through IoT/Edge devices and makes adjustment decisions.

Additionally, there are some known systems:

- **AMR - Autonomous Mobile Robot**
- **Industrial Robot Collaborative Arm**
Have voting rights
 - Integrated by the same company, but they are manufactured and developed by different companies.
 - Voting rights depend on the degree of knowledge and control that the DAO governance requires.

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- Assist the operator: Automatic sanding system
- Surface-Inspection Camera

It is foreseen to setup the following platform, systems and components:

- **OASEES Orchestrator**
 - DAO functionality for HITL decision making
 - Governance
 - Initiates manufacturing order
 - Monitors status
 - Suggests proposals
 - Records decisions
- **Maestro Connect Edge Device**
 - Edge accelerator for roughness inspection
- **OASEES AI Load balancer**
 - Integrated by Maestro Connect
 - Stores and processes information from Arm and camera

SC STACK: UC5 COMPONENT INTERACTION FOR SMART CONTRACT AND DAPP SPECIFICATION

From the expression of the use case above, we extract the interaction schema as shown in Figure 10. Initially we show DAO, DApp and other component interactions.

1. **UC5: DAO activities/proposals for swarm intelligence for UC5.** The set of activities expressed via DAO via proposals and the invocation of the DApp.
 - proposal: propose new requirements instruction
 - proposal: add or remove new edge device
 - proposal: add or remove ARM or related devices

2. Interaction of the whole smart contract stack and other components.

Figure 10 shows interactions between components involved in UC5. These interactions reflect activities related to data sharing based on several events happening related to UC5 description.

Authentication: Any device that participated in this process shall be uniquely authenticated.

- Maestro Connect Edge Device is authenticated via DID Method and associated via “send VC credentials” with DAO as trusted device.
- AMR is authenticated via DID Method and associated via “send VC credentials” with DAO as trusted device.
- Industrial Robot Collaborative is authenticated via DID Method and associated via “send VC credentials” with DAO as trusted device.

Interactions

- ORACLE: DAO monitors the status of ARM and Industrial Robot Collaborative Arm via “monitor status of operations”.
- ARM and Industrial Robot Collaborative Arm provide data for Maestro Connect Edge Device via “provide periodic data”.
- ORACLE: Maestro Connect Edge Device stored data into IPFS by using “store data”.
- HITL can request detailed report via DAO for the state of devices via “request report”.

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- HITL accesses continuously data into IPFS via “data access” mainly by exploiting OASEES Orchestrator.
- ORACLE: ARM “send parameters for proposal” to Maestro Connect Edge Device.
- ORACLE: Industrial Robot Collaborative Arm “send parameters for proposal” to Maestro Connect Edge Device.

//Note: DAO proposal from devices shall go via “Maestro”. For example, ARM and Industrial Robot Collaborative Arm sends parameters which trigger “proposal creation” from Maestro. Then via ORACLE information are sent to DAO.

- Maestro Connect Edge Device “trigger DAO proposal” with parameters gathered from ARM and Maestro Connect Edge Device.
- HITL performs “proposal evaluation” and send decision to “DAO” via “accept/reject”.
- DAO records this decision “record decision” which is further used for notifying involved devices via “send decision parameter”.
- HITL can “proposal: instruction update”, the decision is recorded via “record decision”
- DAO “send proposal info” Maestro Connect Edge Device which further expands decision “send decision parameter” towards involved devices.
- HITL “proposal: add/remove device”.

Note: We use the oracle only in case we cannot access “off-chain” data via DAO or DApp.

Figure 10: Expression of SC stack interaction and other components for UC5.

UC6: SMART ENERGY HARVESTING AND PREDICTIVE-MAINTENANCE WIND TURBINES

The use case covers the maintenance of wind farms supported by a swarm of IoT devices that use the blade acoustic-monitoring system. Figure 11 presents a detailed use-case diagram for wind-turbine maintenance, including required components that are substantial parts of this use case. The main components are the OASEES Portal (DLT, SSI, DApp, and DAO), Swarm (IoT devices), Edge devices, and Cloud Computing.

Figure 11: The use-case diagram for UC6.

In the scenario, the following actors are relevant:

- **OASEES Stakeholders**
 - Access the portal to request algorithm services, results and reports
 - Owner asking for monitoring and maintenance of wind farm
 - Operator
 - Local communities
 - Energy buyers
 - Maintenance providers
 - Involved in DAO Proposals for improvement of the ecosystem
 - Voting on new maintenance plans
 - Voting on deploying new version of services, ML models
 - Voting on creating new services
- **GAIA – X Stakeholder**
 - Energy company interested in data product of another energy company

Access to the Ocean Marketplace and purchase data product
Data Federation with GAIA-X EDC Connector
Not involved in DAO proposals

- **Specialist**
Specialist on wind turbines and their failures.
Human in the Loop (HITL)
Labels and classifies new types of newly detected anomalies
Take decisions over the devices in the DAO for monitoring schedules
Access necessary data without purchasing
Check result reports and maintenance plans to verify their quality
Involved in DAO proposals
Specific VC attributes give HITL powers
- **Installer**
Setup, pre-configuration, and on/off-boarding of IoT and edge devices
- **Developer**
Develops and publishes services
Develop new functionalities of both the pilot algorithms (audio optimization, classifier, and prediction) and the blockchain

Additionally, there are some known systems:

- **IoT Device**
Blade Acoustic-Monitoring System BAMS
Is the device in charge of acquiring the wind turbine acoustic data.
Initiate poll in case of identified wind turbines being off
Vote on going into standby
Vote to retrain algorithms if classification confidence decay
- **Edge Device**
Assigned to one swarm of IoT devices with the BAMS
Receives the raw IoT data
Has an attached accelerator
Manages the federated learning between IoT devices and the accelerator
 - In the same wind farm (CAP priority) train in the devices and aggregate in the edge
 - Between different wind farms (scalability) train in the edge devices and aggregate in one of the edge devices.
- **Accelerator**
Machine-learning algorithm
Failure prediction
Generates a consolidated algorithm from fragmented algorithms
- **Cloud**
Provides services, e.g., failure-prediction algorithm
Off-chain storage

It is foreseen to setup the following platform, systems and components:

- **OASEES Portal**
 - DAO
 - One DAO per wind farm
 - Resource orchestration
 - SSI agent
 - DAO Polls: voting by stakeholders and IoT devices; taking the decision to disconnect or reconnect
 - Wind-turbine blades test report.

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- DApp
 - Monitors health status of blade wind turbines with information sent by BAMS devices
 - Shows meteorological conditions of wind farm.
 - Show geographical position of devices
 - Notebook
 - Marketplace

Data structures:

- **Verifiable Credentials**
 - Describe the attributes of the IoT and edge devices and the wind farm where it is located
 - Access the portal to request algorithm services, result reports
 - Needed by specialists to access the data without purchasing it, to supervise the results of the algorithms and labelling new anomalies
 - Needed by edge devices for uploading aggregated algorithms to the marketplace.
- **Data products:**
 - Technical reports based on the processed acoustic dataset (on-chain/off-chain)
 - Wind-turbine blades anomalies detection (on-chain/off-chain):
 - Maintenance prediction and impact on LCOE (Levelized Cost of Energy) (on-chain/off-chain)
 - Dynamic maintenance plan according to blade health status (on-chain/off-chain)
 - Anonymized blade-acoustic data (Off-chain)

Data Requirements:

From the perspective of data management, specific data needs to be stored off-chain or on-chain. For the given use case, we have an expression of data governance.

SC STACK: UC6 COMPONENT INTERACTION FOR SMART CONTRACT AND DAPP SPECIFICATION

From the use-case expression above, we extract an interaction schema, as shown in Figure 12. Initially, we show interactions between DAO, DApp, and other components.

1. UC6: DAO activities/proposals for swarm intelligence for UC6. The set of activities expressed via DAO via proposals and the invocation of the DApp.

- proposal: DAO joining members
- proposal: New maintenance protocol
- proposal: DAO data-access voting
- proposal: new model voting

2. Interaction of the whole smart contract stack and other components.

Authentication: All components such as stakeholders and IoT devices shall be authenticated via DID method proposed in OASSES identity layer.

- **IoT devices:** Any IoT device is checked (verified), authenticated and then installed via “verify, configure and install IoT Devices”.
- **Edge Devices:** Any edge device is checked (verified), authenticated and installed via “Install and configure Edge Devices”
- **Stakeholders:** Any stakeholders involved need to be authenticated (via Identity Layer)

Interactions

- **HITL Specialist:** initiates a “proposal: DAO joining members”. Stakeholders shall join the DAO via “stakeholders joining DAO”
- **HITL Specialist:** proposes initial maintenance protocol via “propose maintenance protocol” recorded in DAO. All DAO members can vote on the proposal via “proposal: New maint. protocol”
- **Maintenance Operators:** get a notification via “notify maintenance actors” once the proposal is accepted.

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- **IoT Device:** “sense data” and “send data to edge”. Edge device performs action on “identify data set” and stores hashing in the blockchain via Smart Contract/DApp. Dataset ID enlisted in DAO via “data identification”
- **EDGE Device BAMS** “exploit/execute” which checks for “check for issues/failures prediction”.
- **Accelerator:** In case any failure is detected (predicted, evidenced) then Accelerator notifies “notify details of failure”
- **Smart Contract/DApp:** enables “hashing” of dataset.
- **Developers:** can “request data access”, and DAO shall notify “HITL Specialist” for the data access via “notify: data request”. They exploit Smart Contract/DApp interfaces to perform such actions
- **DAO:** its members can evaluate and allow or deny access to specific data via “proposal: DAO data access voting”
- **Developers:** can propose new maintenance algorithm via “dev: propose new maintenance model”. The model can be initially evaluated from HITL Specialist
- **HITL Specialist:** propose new maintenance model via “propose new maintenance model”
- **DAO:** all members can vote on the new maintenance model via “proposal: new model voting”
- **Smart Contract/DApp:** is exploited to distribute decision on new maintenance protocol, including instruction for maintenance, algorithmic data, off-chain instruction via “distribute DAO decision new model”.
- **Maintenance Operator:** receives notification via “new maint. model adapted”, which can further adapt their operations.

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Figure 12: Expression of SC stack interaction and other components for UC6.

OASEES: SMART CONTRACT API AND ORACLE SPECIFICATION BASED ON GIVEN REQUIREMENTS

In the context of OASEES data are primarily (depending on certain stage of use case development) stored off-chain. As reported in the literature (Caldarelli, 2020), various problems with the current architecture of blockchains emerge precisely whenever there is the need for interactions with the world outside the BC system. In such cases, trust must be delegated to Oracles (Mammadzada, 2020), which are located outside smart contracts i.e., off-chain. Several approaches for implementing Oracles for blockchain-based systems have been identified in the literature (Caldarelli, 2020). In this section we detail specifications for such an Oracle component that addresses the needs of the identified use cases.

THE ORACLE TERMINOLOGY

Figure 13 shows oracle-components' terminology¹⁵ used in OASEES. A Dataset (often referred to as “Digital-Asset Record”) is a piece of digital information that is stored in an external system.

A Tokenized Dataset (often referred to as “Tokenized-Asset Record”) is a piece of digital information that contains data that need to be persisted (e.g., as evidence, proof of existence, etc.) and therefore registered in the Oracle as part of its off-chain storage. As not all information may be kept in the Oracle, the Tokenized Dataset may contain a subset of the original (external) dataset. Thus, whenever necessary, a Tokenized Dataset may contain a permanent reference to its dataset.

A Token is the data structure on the network (i.e., on-chain) that represents the dataset through its association with the Tokenized Dataset. A given token must have a permanent immutable link (reference) to a Tokenized Dataset. Since the asset token is an on-chain construct, it can be managed by a smart contract or other similar programs that interact with the ledger of the on-chain network.

Figure 13: The oracle on-chain and off-chain components.

ORACLE-DATA ARCHITECTURE

¹⁵ Terminology is derived from RFC: <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/draft-avrilionis-satp-asset-schema-architecture/>

The semantic structure of Tokenized Datasets (TDSs) is based on the notion of Dataset Schema and Dataset Profile. The Dataset Schema defines the base for all Internationalized Resource Identifiers (IRIs) defined in RFC 3987: Internationalized Resource Identifiers (IRIs). Dataset Profiles further refine data structures that are specialized in specific domains. Some generic data structures that apply to all Dataset Profiles are defined in the Dataset Schema. For example, the definition of an **organization key** (JSON-based field within Dataset Schema) that is used to identify the organization that owns the Dataset Profile is defined as a generic attribute at the level of the Dataset Schema.

The overall structure of the data architecture is as shown in Figure 14. Basically, a dataset schema is the high-level root of the type of hierarchy (it can be seen as the “thing” class in OWL¹⁶). The DataSet profile is a specialization of a schema that defines the type a tokenized DataSet. A tokenized dataset is defined at the level of each use case. In an object-oriented view a profile is a “class”. A Tokenized Dataset is an “instance” of a Profile. The relationship between a profile and a tokenized dataset is (ontologically) a class-instance relationship.

Figure 14: Oracle dataset typing structure.

DATASET SCHEMA

The Data Schema is defined in JSON-LD as follows:

```
{
  "@context": {
    "@version": 1.1,
```

¹⁶ <https://www.w3.org/TR/owl-semantics/examples.html>

```

"foaf": "http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/",
"schema": "http://schema.org/",
"skos": "http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#",
"xsd": "http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#",
"rdf": "http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#",
"organization_key": {
  "@id": "https://example.org/dataset_schema_org_key",
  "@context": {
    "public_key": {
      "@id": "https://example.org/dataset_schema_pub_key",
      "@type": "schema:string"
    },
    "issued": {
      "@id": "https://example.org/dataset_schema_key_issued",
      "@type": "schema:string"
    }
  }
},
"qualities": {
  "@id": "https://example.org/dataset_schema_qualities"
}
},
"@id": "https://example.org/dataset_schema/"
}

```

The **organisation key** is defined as a data structure with two attributes:

- the *public_key* attribute refers to the public key of the organization that owns the dataset profile;
- the *issued* attribute refers to the data of issuance of the key.

DATASET PROFILE

The Dataset Profile specializes the DataSchema in a specific context and for a given purpose per use case. A Dataset Profile can be used to define various objects, from digital records to physical ones. The example below shows a definition of a Dataset Profile for physical assets from provider acme.com.

```

{
  "@context": {
    "@version": 1.1,
    "tds": "https://example.org/dataset_schema/",
    "physical_asset": {
      "@id": "https://acme.com/dataset_profile/physical_asset",
      "@context": {
        "digital_carrier_id": {
          "@id": "https://acme.com/dataset_profile/digital_carrier_id",
          "@type": "schema:string"
        },
        "digital_carrier_type": {
          "@id": "https://acme.com/dataset_profile/digital_carrier_type",
          "@type": "schema:string"
        },
        "physical_asset_kind": {
          "@id": "https://acme.com/dataset_profile/physical_asset_kind",
          "@container": "@language"
        },
        "physical_asset_description": {
          "@id": "https://acme.com/dataset_profile/physical_asset_description",
          "@container": "@language"
        },
        "physical_asset_location": {
          "@id": "https://acme.com/dataset_profile/physical_asset_location",
          "@container": "@language"
        }
      }
    }
  }
}

```

```

    }
  },
  "@id": "https://acme.com/dataset_profile/physical_asset",
  "schema:title": "Dataset Profile for physical assets",
  "schema:organization": {
    "@id": "https://acme.com/",
    "schema:email": "info@acme.com",
    "tds:organization_key": {
      "tds:public_key": "did:v1:test:nym:JApJf12r82Pe6PBJ3gJAAwo8F7uDnae6B4ab9EFQ7XXk#authn-key-1",
      "tds:issued": "2018-03-15T00:00:00Z"
    }
  },
  "tds:qualities": {
    "is_movable": true,
    "is_replacable": true,
    "is_monitored": true
  }
}

```

As shown above, besides the attributes defining the physical asset, the dataset profile also defines some qualities for the given profile, i.e. the physical asset can be moved to a different location, can be replaced, and is monitored for security purposes.

ADDITIONAL CONSIDERATIONS – BRIDGE ARCHITECTURE

Figure 15 describes the high-level oracle architecture. The Oracle, as it stands, is a passive component that receives datasets, stores them in its internal off-chain storage, and creates tokens associated with the received datasets. However, it lacks an active notification mechanism based on any sort of logic associated with the received data. To address this, we propose the introduction of a **bridge layer**. This layer would not only interpret the data but also notify any interested party about the fact that the Oracle has received a given dataset, thereby enhancing the functionality of the system.

Our proposal to augment the OASEES architecture with a **bridge** component brings significant benefits. This component would enable seamless exchanges with external systems, whether they are off-chain or on-chain. It would interpret the data and notify interested parties when the Oracle receives a dataset, enhancing the functionality and efficiency of the system.

Figure 15: Oracle high-level architecture.

BASIC FLOWS

Figure 16 shows the basic interaction flows for the Oracle/Bridge components:

Figure 16: Oracle/bridge basic flows.

OFF-CHAIN INITIATED CALL SEQUENCE

1: An external system sends a Tokenized Dataset to the Oracle

A: The Oracle (off-chain bridge module) receives and stores the Tokenized Dataset

B: The Oracle (on-chain tokenization module) creates a token associated with the Tokenized Dataset

ON-CHAIN INITIATED CALL SEQUENCE

2: A DAO calls the on-chain Oracle (via the on-chain bridge module) to verify the existence of on-chain data.

3: A DApp calls the on-chain Oracle (via the on-chain bridge module) to verify the existence of on-chain data.

C: The on-chain bridge module verifies the existence of tokens or requests creation of tokens.

D: The off-chain bridge is either notified or is periodically checking any request for new token creation.

E: In the case of token creation request the off-chain bridge may call back the external system to request creation of new Tokenized Datasets.

F: Similar to A

G: Similar to B. When necessary, the Token is associated to the original DAO (2) or DApp (3) request.

H: If the DAO (2) or DApp (3) need to be notified of the creation of new tokens, then, the on-chain tokenization modules calls the on-chain bridge module to propagate the notification.

I: The on-chain bridge notifies the creation of the new token to the original requester DAO (2).

J: The on-chain bridge notifies the creation of the new token to the original requester DApp (3).

ARCHITECTURE CONSIDERATIONS

Below we list some elements that need to be considered when implementing the Oracle/Bridge component.

OFF-CHAIN

- The datasets sent to Oracle should have a clear ownership structure. The most straightforward way is to have them signed by the owner (see the organization key element of the Data Schema above). If there are cases of multiple ownership, a multi-signature mechanism should be implemented.
- Clarify the role of the Bridge/Oracle in meeting the real-time/heavy load requirements of (off-chain) external systems. In this scenario, the Bridge/Oracle should implement a high availability / high throughput for its (off-chain) API. This means that API calls should be designed to immediately return, without awaiting any blockchain confirmation via synchronous RPC calls, thereby ensuring efficient system performance.

ON-CHAIN

- Implementing tokenization of datasets using ERC721¹⁷ SCs should be thoroughly evaluated as there might be cases where datasets should be mutable (updatable). One option for such mutable datasets is to cater for multiple tokens, one for each version of the dataset.
- In case several datasets must be created at once, the whole Bridge/Oracle architecture should allow the creation of tokens in batch mode.
- It should be clarified whether the role of the dataset creator and token administrator is given to the dataset owner or not.

ORACLE IMPLEMENTATION

The diagram shown in Figure 17 presents the sequence of actions executed when an external system (stakeholder) calls an off-chain bridge. As can be seen from the diagram, upon reception of the JSON dataset (1), the Oracle fetches the Dataset profile from the off-chain storage (2) and verifies that incoming dataset in JSON format confirms to its profile (3).

It's worth noting that the profile verification process is not always mandatory. In some instances, the Oracle stores semantically unverified datasets. This is particularly relevant when a stakeholder assumes full accountability/responsibility for the accuracy of the information stored in their systems, and the Oracle serves as the ultimate source of truth for regulatory compliance.

Once the above steps are completed, the Oracle stores the JSON dataset in its off-chain storage (4) and returns a temporary receipt ID to the caller (5).

Then, the Oracle calls a SC on-chain (blockchain) to mint a token related to the Dataset (6). Given the asynchronous nature of blockchain confirmation, the Oracle should wait for the token-minting transaction to be confirmed. Once the transaction is confirmed (7), the Oracle stores the final dataset Oracle ID (containing a reference to the on-chain

¹⁷ <https://docs.openzeppelin.com/contracts/4.x/erc721>

token) in the off-chain storage component (8). At any stage after creating the Dataset Oracle ID, the stakeholder can call the Oracle to receive the dataset Oracle ID from the receipt ID (9).

Figure 17: Oracle-dataset registration - main flow.

The sequence diagram shown in Figure 17, presents a detailed example of the off-chain bridge API of the Oracle. Below we give an open-API specification of the complete off-chain bridge API¹⁸.

```

{
  "openapi": "3.0.3",
  "info": {
    "title": "OASEES ORACLE API - OpenAPI 3.0",
    "description": "This is a sample Registry API as defined in the OASEES Oracle Architecture. The API is based on the OpenAPI 3.0 specification",
    "termsOfService": "https://oasees.org/oracle/terms",
    "contact": {
      "email": "hello@oasees-project.eu"
    },
    "license": {
      "name": "License:TBD",
      "url": "https://oasees.org/oracle/licenses/license.html"
    }
  },
}

```

¹⁸ The presented JSON is exploitable using Swagger editor: <https://editor.swagger.io/>

```

    "version": "1.0.0"
  },
  "externalDocs": {
    "description": "OASEES",
    "url": "https://oasees-project.eu/"
  },
  "servers": [
    {
      "url": "https://oasees-project.eu/oracles/v1"
    }
  ],
  "tags": [
    {
      "name": "dataset",
      "description": "Dataset Management",
      "externalDocs": {
        "description": "Find out more",
        "url": "https://oasees-project.eu/"
      }
    }
  ],
  "paths": {
    "/dataset": {
      "post": {
        "tags": [
          "dataset"
        ],
        "summary": "Add a new Dataset to the Oracle",
        "description": "This method stores the input data off-chain and returns a receipt_id. It initiates (asynchronously) the on-chain creation of the token associated to the Dataset. However, the method should return as soon as the input data are stored off-chain. Since the dataset id is built using on-chain data from the token, the method should return `receipt_id` (a temporary id) that would be substituted with the permanent `datasetId` once the on-chain token is confirmed",
        "operationId": "addDataset",
        "requestBody": {
          "description": "Create a new Dataset in the store",
          "content": {
            "application/json": {
              "schema": {
                "$ref": "#/components/schemas/DatasetRequest"
              }
            }
          },
          "required": true
        },
        "responses": {
          "202": {
            "description": "Operation queued for execution, returned receipt ID",
            "content": {
              "text/plain": {
                "schema": {
                  "type": "string",
                  "example": "urn:dataset:cmpl:uuid:018df63e-9a4f-75ab-8b9f-9b369ca40e33"
                }
              }
            }
          },
          "400": {
            "description": "Invalid input"
          },
          "422": {
            "description": "Validation exception"
          }
        }
      }
    }
  },
},

```

```

"/datasetID/{receiptID}": {
  "get": {
    "tags": [
      "dataset"
    ],
    "summary": "Find DatasetID by receiptID",
    "description": "Returns the DatasetID",
    "operationId": "getDatasetIDByReceiptID",
    "parameters": [
      {
        "name": "receiptID",
        "in": "path",
        "description": "receipt ID of a Dataset",
        "required": true,
        "schema": {
          "type": "string",
          "example": "urn:dataset:cmpl:uuid:018df63e-9a4f-75ab-8b9f-9b369ca40e33"
        }
      }
    ],
    "responses": {
      "200": {
        "description": "successful operation",
        "content": {
          "text/plain": {
            "schema": {
              "type": "string",
              "example":
"urn:dataset:eip155.137:ns.oasees:0x416BBF0c9B71f64b5807f644E1F1bacD3Afb3ea9"
            }
          }
        },
        "400": {
          "description": "Invalid receipt ID"
        },
        "404": {
          "description": "Dataset ID not found"
        }
      }
    }
  },
  "/dataset/{datasetID}": {
    "get": {
      "tags": [
        "dataset"
      ],
      "summary": "Find Dataset by ID",
      "description": "Returns a single Dataset",
      "operationId": "getDatasetById",
      "parameters": [
        {
          "name": "datasetID",
          "in": "path",
          "description": "ID of Dataset to return",
          "required": true,
          "schema": {
            "type": "string",
            "example":
"urn:tar:eip155.137:ns.oasees:0x416BBF0c9B71f64b5807f644E1F1bacD3Afb3ea9"
          }
        }
      ],
      "responses": {
        "200": {
          "description": "successful operation",
          "content": {

```

```

        "application/json": {
          "schema": {
            "$ref": "#/components/schemas/Dataset"
          }
        }
      },
      "400": {
        "description": "Invalid Dataset ID"
      },
      "404": {
        "description": "Dataset not found"
      }
    }
  },
  "delete": {
    "tags": [
      "dataset"
    ],
    "summary": "Archive a Dataset",
    "description": "Archive a Dataset without deleting the data. The on-chain token associated to that Dataset may be burnt.",
    "operationId": "archiveDataset",
    "parameters": [
      {
        "name": "datasetID",
        "in": "path",
        "description": "ID of the Dataset to archive",
        "required": true,
        "schema": {
          "type": "string",
          "example": "urn:dataset:eip155.137:ns.oasees:0x416BBF0c9B71f64b5807f644E1F1bacD3Afb3ea9"
        }
      }
    ],
    "responses": {
      "204": {
        "description": "successful operation - no return value"
      },
      "404": {
        "description": "Dataset not found"
      },
      "410": {
        "description": "Dataset already archived"
      }
    }
  }
}
},
"components": {
  "schemas": {
    "DatasetRequest": {
      "title": "Dataset creation Request",
      "type": "object",
      "properties": {
        "data": {
          "type": "string",
          "example": {
            "@context": "urn:dataset:eip155.137:ns.oasees:0x517BBF0c9B71f64b5807f644E1F1bacD3Afb3ec2",
            "physical_asset": {
              "digital_carrier_id": "E492069BT491278256346325",
              "digital_carrier_type": "rfid_tag",
              "physical_asset_kind": [
                "en",
                "gate"
              ]
            }
          }
        }
      }
    }
  }
}

```


OASEES: ORACLE SPECIFICATION FOR THE OASEES USE CASES

In the table below, we present the Oracle specification for the OASEES use case. This table also presents the use-case element and any associated data on third-party services that are stored off-chain and on-chain, respectively.

UC1: SMART-EDGE-CONNECTED NODE FOR THE ANALYSIS OF VOICE, ARTICULATION AND FLUENCY DISORDERS IN PARKINSON’S DISEASE

Use-Case Element	ORACLE accessing data on third-party service and storing them Off-Chain		ORACLE accessing data on third-party service and storing them On-Chain	
	Oracle behaviour description	Input/Output	Oracle behaviour description	Input/Output
SSI: Identified by a DID: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> the device the patient the therapist the scientist the hospital the algorithm supplier <p><i>This list is not exhaustive</i></p>	Before calling the Oracle, each stakeholder must be able to generate its key pair, its DID and store securely its private key. It must also be able to call the Blockchain to store the that DID and the DID document on chain.	IN: Public Key DID / DID Doc Mac Address if applicable Temp out: Dataset Oracle receipt ID Perm OUT: Dataset Oracle ID	Creation of a token representing the device	IN: Ref. to off chain Dataset OUT: Tokenization
Smart Edge Device	The device must be able to hash the audio file and send this hash to the Blockchain via “store hashes to BV device reg”	IN: Device DID / DID Doc Hash of the Annotated Audio file Temp out: Dataset Oracle receipt ID	Creation of a token representing the audio file	IN: Ref. to off chain Dataset OUT: Tokenization

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		Perm OUT: Dataset Oracle ID		
Smart Edge Device	The device must be able to send the model to the Blockchain	IN: Device DID / DID Doc Model Temp out: Dataset Oracle receipt ID Perm OUT: Dataset Oracle ID	Creation of a token representing the model.	IN: Ref. to off chain Dataset OUT: Tokenization
The Therapist	Each time the Therapist will act on the smart device result to score, to write feedback, to adapt exercise,, the oracle will be called to record those actions under defined activity codes. These records will allow monetization of the Therapist activities.	IN: Activity code, Score, Feedback Temp out: Dataset Oracle receipt ID Perm OUT: Dataset Oracle id	Creation of a token representing each Therapist activity.	IN: Dataset Oracle ID OUT: Tokenization
Algorithm Supplier	Each Time a new version of the algorithm is delivered or downloaded; the action must be tracked by the oracle in	IN: Algorithm version, date, ... Temp out:	Creation of a token representing each algorithm delivery or download.	IN: Dataset Oracle ID OUT:

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	order to allow the monetization of the algorithm development.	Dataset Oracle receipt ID Perm OUT: Dataset Oracle ID		Tokenization
--	---	--	--	--------------

UC2: EVS FLEET COORDINATED RECHARGING TO SUPPORT OPTIMAL OPERATION OF ELECTRICITY GRID

Use Case Element	ORACLE accessing data on third-party service and storing them Off-Chain		ORACLE accessing data on third-party service and storing them On-Chain	
	Oracle behaviour description	Input/Output	Oracle behaviour description	Input/Output
SSI: Identified by a DID: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DSO • eMSP • CPO • EV (Electric Vehicle) • CS (Charging Station) • Smart Meter • <i>This is list is not exhaustive</i>	Before to call the Oracle, each stakeholder must be able to generate itself its key pair, its DID and store securely its private key. It must also be able to call the Blockchain to store the that DID and the DID document on chain.	IN: Public Key DID / DID Doc Mac Address if applicable Temp out: Dataset Oracle receipt ID Perm OUT: Dataset Oracle ID	Creation of a token representing the device	IN: Ref. to off chain Dataset OUT: Tokenization
From CPO - Charging Point Operator Smart Meter Charging Station (Raspberry)	Read data from Charging Station and send it to blockchain.	IN: Energy Amount Provided Real Time consumption Charging session start and end. Temp out: Dataset Oracle receipt ID Perm OUT: Dataset Oracle ID	Read data from Charging Station and send it to blockchain.	IN: Ref. to off chain Dataset OUT: Tokenization

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<p>Electric Vehicle (EV) (on-boarded IoT)</p>	<p>Onboarded IoT send every 5 sec battery level (%)</p>	<p>IN: State of charge (%) Mileage</p> <p>Temp out: Dataset Oracle receipt ID</p> <p>Perm OUT: Dataset Oracle ID</p>	<p>Record State of charge</p>	<p>IN: Ref. to off chain Dataset</p> <p>OUT: Tokenization DAO input</p>
<p>DSO: Distributed System Operator / Electricity Network Operator - Manages the energy grid.</p> <p>Yellow on picture</p>	<p>Provide energy data from grid.</p> <p>PV plants / Buildings</p>	<p>In: Energy consumption/ production on a regular basis.</p> <p>Temp out: Dataset Oracle receipt ID</p> <p>Perm OUT: Dataset Oracle ID</p>	<p>Record energy data from grid.</p> <p>Issue Flexibility Request</p>	<p>IN: Ref to off chain Dataset</p> <p>OUT: Tokenization DAO input</p>
<p>eMSP - e-Mobility Service Provider - Manages the business side of the changing network with its charging stations for electric vehicles.</p> <p>Owner of the digital platform able to create flexibility provision.</p>	<p>Plan charging session according to DSO needs</p>	<p>In: Charging session availability.</p> <p>Temp out: Dataset Oracle receipt ID</p> <p>Perm OUT: Dataset Oracle ID</p>	<p>Offer Flexibility Service</p>	<p>IN: Ref to off chain Dataset</p> <p>OUT: Tokenization DAO input</p>

UC3: DRONE SWARM OVER 5G FOR HIGH MAST INSPECTION

Use Case Element	ORACLE accessing data on third-party service and storing them Off-Chain		ORACLE accessing data on third-party service and storing them On-Chain	
	Oracle behaviour description	Input/Output	Oracle behaviour description	Input/Output
SSI: Identified by a DID: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Drone Pilot • Drone / Drone Swarm • UAV Service Supplier • Customer • Authorization Entity <i>This is list is not exhaustive</i>	Before to call the Oracle, each stakeholder must be able to generate itself its key pair, its DID and store securely its private key. It must also be able to call the Blockchain to store the that DID and the DID document on chain.	IN: Public Key DID / DID Doc Mac Address if applicable Temp out: Dataset Oracle receipt ID Perm OUT: Dataset Oracle ID	Creation of a token representing the device	IN: Ref. to off chain Dataset OUT: Tokenization
Drone Drone Swarm	Must be able to send raw data to IPFS	IN: Raw Data Temp out: Dataset Oracle receipt ID Perm OUT: Dataset Oracle ID	Creation of a token representing the raw data Request Actions & Routes to QPU	IN: Ref. to off chain Dataset OUT: Tokenization
QPU Quantum Processing Unit (Optimized Routes)	Store Optimized Route Off Chain	IN: Optimized Route Temp out: Dataset Oracle receipt ID Perm OUT:	Send Optimized Route to Blockchain	IN: Ref to off chain Dataset OUT: Tokenization

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		Dataset Oracle ID		
SNNs Spike Neutral Network (Pattern Detection)	Store Detection Results Off Chain	IN: Detection Results Temp out: Dataset Oracle receipt ID Perm OUT: Dataset Oracle ID	Store Detection Results On Chain	IN: Ref to off chain Dataset OUT: Tokenization

UC4: THE STRUCTURAL SAFETY ASSESSMENT FOR BUILDINGS

Use Case Element	ORACLE accessing data on third-party service and storing them Off-Chain		ORACLE accessing data on third-party service and storing them On-Chain	
	Oracle behaviour description	Input/Output	Oracle behaviour description	Input/Output
SSI: Identified by a DID: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> the device the customer External Agencies, Decision Makers Sensors <p><i>This is list is not exhaustive</i></p>	Before to call the Oracle, each stakeholder must be able to generate itself its key pair, its DID and store securely its private key. It must also be able to call the Blockchain to store the that DID and the DID document on chain.	IN: Public Key DID / DID Doc Mac Address if applicable Temp out: Dataset Oracle receipt ID Perm OUT: Dataset Oracle ID	Creation of a token representing the device	IN: Ref to off-chain dataset OUT: Token
Accelerometers Laser deformation sensors	The raw data collected by the sensors during an earthquake event is stored off-chain.	IN: Raw data from sensor OUT: CID	Sensor data hashes are very relevant and need to be on-chain since they are also attached to a context from which critical information about the structure in question can be derived.	IN: Sensor data hash Context OUT: Transaction ID
Smart Edge Device (Raspberry PI)	External-agency data: Any data or reports provided by external	IN: Any data or reports provided by external agencies	The device must be able to store Event Data Hashes on-chain.	IN: Event data hash OUT:

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	<p>agencies, such as rescue teams or structural-assessment teams, are stored off-chain.</p>	<p>OUT: CID</p>	<p>Changes to the NW system: Any updates or modifications to the NW system, such as changes to the data-processing algorithms or updates to the system’s capabilities, can also be recorded on-chain.</p> <p>HITL communication, back and forth, is needed.</p> <p>The device must be able to receive alerts like internal operation & maintenance teams initiating post-event inspection operations, activating additional data-processing routines.</p> <p>Earthquake detection must be received by the device and recorded on-chain.</p>	<p>Transaction ID</p> <p>IN: Any change to the NW System Vote result from DAO Alert Earthquake detection by Agencies</p> <p>OUT: Transaction ID</p>
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UC5: ROBOTIC SWARM POWERED FACTORY FOR I4.0

Use Case Element	ORACLE accessing data on third party service and storing them Off-Chain		ORACLE accessing data on third party service and storing them On-Chain	
	Oracle behaviour description	Input/Output	Oracle behaviour description	Input/Output
SSI: Identified by a DID: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Autonomous Mobile Robots (AMRs) Industrial Robot Collaborative: arm SCM System Worker Smart Edge Device <i>This is list is not exhaustive</i>	Before to call the Oracle, each stakeholder must be able to generate itself its key pair, its DID and store securely its private key. It must also be able to call the Blockchain to store the that DID and the DID document on chain.	IN: Public Key DID / DID Doc Mac Address if applicable Temp out: Dataset Oracle receipt ID Perm OUT: Dataset Oracle ID	Creation of a token representing the device	IN: Ref to off chain Dataset OUT: Tokenization
Robot / Arm	stored data into IPFS by using “store data”	IN: Energy consumption data Temp out: Dataset Oracle receipt ID Perm OUT: Dataset Oracle ID	Creation of a token representing the data	IN: Ref to off chain Dataset OUT: Tokenization

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Autonomous Mobile Robots (AMRs)	Sending data	<p>IN: Odometry data</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Navigation data • Robot arm log • Map of working area (txt + image) <p><i>This list might still evolve during the UC development.</i></p> <p>Temp out: Dataset Oracle receipt ID</p> <p>Perm OUT: Dataset Oracle ID</p>	Creation of a token representing the Robot/Arm	<p>IN: Ref to off chain Dataset</p> <p>OUT: Tokenization</p>
Worker	Inspection Report	<p>IN: Inspection report.</p> <p>Temp out: Dataset Oracle receipt ID</p> <p>Perm OUT: Dataset Oracle ID</p>	Creation of a token representing the report	<p>IN: Ref to off chain Dataset</p> <p>OUT: Tokenization</p>

UC6: SMART ENERGY HARVESTING AND PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE WIND TURBINES

Use Case Element	ORACLE accessing data on third party service and storing them Off-Chain		ORACLE accessing data on third party service and storing them On-Chain	
	Oracle behaviour description	Input/Output	Oracle behaviour description	Input/Output
SSI: Identified by a DID: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sensors (acceleration, temperature, pressure, rotation speed or current intensity) • Specialist • Installer • Edge device • Developer <i>This is list is not exhaustive</i>	Before to call the Oracle, each stakeholder must be able to generate itself its key pair, its DID and store securely its private key. It must also be able to call the Blockchain to store the that DID and the DID document on chain.	IN: Public Key DID / DID Doc Mac Address if applicable Temp out: Dataset Oracle receipt ID Perm OUT: Dataset Oracle ID	Creation of a token representing the device	IN: Ref. to off chain Dataset OUT: Token
Edge server from the wind farm Edge device BAMS (Blade Acoustic Monitoring System) (Raspberry PI4)	Aggregated data on the turbine's energy production	IN: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintenance Record • Data on the condition of the blades • Real-time data from the hundreds of sensors on the wind turbines, monitoring environmental conditions and turbine function. • Images or videos from visual inspections • Acoustic signals: Data captured by the BAMS 	Creation of a token representing the Aggregated data	IN: Ref. to off chain Dataset OUT: Tokenization

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		Temp out: Dataset Oracle receipt ID		
		Perm OUT: Dataset Oracle ID		

CONCLUSIONS AND IMPLICATIONS

In this deliverable, we have expressed the high level of the OASEES Smart Contract/DAO and DApp related to the OASEES use cases. To achieve this, we have proposed a robust and proven methodology that enables the extraction of use-case requirements. This methodology not only allows for a detailed decomposition of the use-case components but also facilitates the examination of the information flow and component interaction. Furthermore, it has allowed us to compose compact use-case functionalities, including component interaction and data flow. This methodology is a key factor in deeply understanding OASEES use cases from the functional viewpoint.

For the detailed use-case specification, we have conducted several meetings with the use cases, where we raised specific questions on the functionality of the use cases, their components, data flows, and potential dependencies. These questions ranged from technical aspects to user experience considerations. For each use case, we have created a use case diagram and a SC specification related to DAO and DApp. We have also listed the sequential interaction for each OASEES use case, expressing the connection, data exchange, and decision making via DAO. This approach has enabled us to extract potential functional requirements that will be implemented in later stages of the project development.

In the context of OASEES, the use cases involve the handling of data both on-chain and off-chain. To manage this, we have introduced the oracle-bridge components. These components serve as a crucial link between the off-chain and on-chain data, ensuring the integrity and security of the data flow. They play a pivotal role in the management of both types of data, facilitating smooth and secure operations of the OASEES system.

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ANNEX 1: DATA STRUCTURE AND TRIGGERING LOGIC FOR THE USE CASE 4 – STRUCTURAL SAFETY

INTRODUCTION

The sensor data used in earthquake monitoring, which is the core business of Senso and the main topic of UC 4, is different than other monitoring cases in a couple of ways. First of all, the seismic-monitoring sensors are usually analogue, with a digitizer attached. This creates an extra step in levelling up the data from raw data to the hashed data. Furthermore, the data produced is of much higher frequency than that of the other sensors, creating a volume of data difficult to handle at the edge, even in a centralized architecture. Seismic sensors usually record 7/24 continuously, with 200Hz sampling rate. Each sensor has 3 channels (X, Y and Z) creating 600 data points per sensor per second.

The data structure of UC 4 is explained here in detail for better understanding its relation to the swarm mode and to the DAO architecture, as well as for identifying which part of the data should be on-chain and which parts should be off-chain.

DATA STRUCTURE AND DATA LEVELS

RAW DATA

An analogue seismic sensor (accelerometer) gives raw data in “counts”. These are integer numbers, which are easier to store and transfer. If an accelerometer has a measurement range $\pm 2g$ and $\pm 10V$ output, for instance, $-10V$ measurement refers to minus $2g$ and $+10V$ measurement refers to plus $2g$. All other measurements are distributed in between. The number of steps between the $-10V$ and $+10V$ has to do with the resolution of the digitizer. The industrial standard is 24bit digitizers, which means that the $20V$ range is divided to $2^{24} = 16,777,216$ steps. Each of these steps is 1 count. A count value of 0 means minus $2g$ acceleration, a count value of $8,388,608$ means $0g$ and a count value of $16,777,216$ means plus $2g$. In some cases, the raw data may also be given (by the data-acquisition software of the sensor vendor) in other units, such as fraction of voltage, etc.

The raw count values are the “Raw Data”. If the properties of the sensor are not known (i.e., the range $\pm 2g$, location, time stamp, position in the building, soil properties beneath, etc.), then the raw data is useless to a third party, hence there is no need to store or transfer it on-chain.

CLEAN DATA

The raw data is usually longer than needed. It also contains noise created by the sensor itself and the environment. In order to proceed with the raw data, first the instrument response is removed. This is done by transferring “counts” to engineering units (i.e., m/sec^2 or g). Furthermore, any linear or nonlinear trend is removed and a bandpass filter (usually between $0.1Hz$ to $25Hz$) is applied. The data is truncated, usually spanning a $120-180sec$ long period, that starts some seconds before the starting time of the earthquake and ends a couple of minutes after. This array of data still misses contextual information (location, time stamp, position in the building, soil properties beneath, etc.), which would render them useful. This is the reason why it can be stored off-chain.

PROCESSED DATA

Once arrays of clean data are produced, some processing is applied over the data to help interpreting it in a further step. The data is integrated over time, and a time history of velocity (instead of acceleration) is obtained. The peak absolute velocity is a parameter very well correlated with structural damage. Furthermore, passing the acceleration data through a process, a response spectrum is produced. A response spectrum shows what kind of structures (i.e., short and stiff ones versus tall and flexible ones) respond to the recorded accelerations. This is the key parameter of seismic design of structures. Furthermore, comparing the response spectrum of one sensor to another (i.e., top floor versus basement), a transfer function is produced for understanding whether the dynamic characteristics of a structure have altered. If they did, this is a sign of damage.

Finally, various scalar parameters are collected from the processed data for understanding the characteristics of the recorded motion and possible effects on the monitored structures. The processed data can be interpreted by a third party for reaching conclusions regarding the safety of the monitored asset, hence the processed data needs to be kept on-chain.

The main difference between the “processed” and “clean” data is that the clean data is still at sensor-channel level, while processed data starts to compare different sensor channels within the same asset to each other and generate new sets of data. Furthermore, the cleaned data is always in the time domain, while the processed data is both in time and frequency domains. These are the reasons one extra step is needed from “clean” to “processed” data.

HASHED DATA

The hashed data is a combination of a set of external data as well as the outcomes of the processed data. Hashed data is usually an array of scalar numbers that contains various information on the recorded motion and its relevance to the recording location, surrounding buildings and the triggering earthquake (magnitude, date/time and location).

TRIGGERING LOGIC

A decision whether an earthquake happened or not can be given by the NightWatch DSS in two ways: quick and detailed triggers. The quick trigger takes place a few seconds after the earthquake, while the detailed trigger can take 1 to 20 minutes, depending on when the earthquake will officially be announced by the national agency.

QUICK TRIGGER

The NightWatch Prelim (NW Prelim) module of the NightWatch software, is running directly on the source where the sensor data is collected. NW Prelim continuously checks the sensor data in short intervals (every few seconds) and looks for anomalies in the data. This is done by trimming pieces of data from the last few seconds (usually last 30 sec) and producing “clean data” from these packages. The clean data is tested against previously established criteria, including machine-learning classification. If an earthquake is detected from the sensor signal, the client is informed via SMS and a short e-mail message. The content of these messages is something in the lines of:

“An earthquake is detected from the sensor data. Max. acceleration is XXX, at the sensor location YYY. Alarm Level: YELLOW. A detailed report will follow.”

The Quick Trigger via NW Prelim is based only on the sensor data and cannot be used for deducing critical information about that earthquake, such as location, magnitude and time of the earthquake. Such information can only be generated by using a nationwide seismometer network, a task conducted by observatories (KOERI, NOA, IGVN, USGS, etc.). This is a piece of external data and is collected and evaluated by NightWatch Event module as explained in the next section.

DETAILED TRIGGER

NightWatch Event module of the NightWatch software runs a watchdog, continuously scanning the information channels of the national observatories. This is done every few seconds. The latest reported earthquakes are compared against pre-defined criteria to learn whether the most recent reported earthquakes are important for the monitored asset or not. Example criteria for defining “important earthquakes” are:

Earthquakes of $M_w \geq 6.0$ within the radius of 300km from the asset, or

Earthquakes of $M_w \geq 5.0$ within the radius of 200km from the asset, or

Earthquakes of $M_w \geq 4.5$ within the radius of 100km from the asset, or

Earthquakes of $M_w \geq 4.0$ within the radius of 50km from the asset.

If an earthquake fitting the above criteria is detected, then the sensor data spreading 30 seconds before and 2.5 minutes after the officially announced earthquake time is extracted from the sensor-data storage. A complete report is prepared including maps and plots of the processed and hashed data. An alarm level is once more given in this detailed report (usually the same level of alarm as the one produced by NW Prelim since the same part of the sensor data was used a few minutes ago). The report is delivered via email or BI (Business Intelligence, such as Power BI) infrastructure.